

Fatty Acid Derivatives of Aluminium, Titanium, and Zirconium

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The existence of tri-, di-, and mono-soaps of aluminium has been in question for a long time. Conflicting opinions have been expressed regarding formation of all the three types. The publications of McBain and McLatchie¹ and others²⁻⁶ over the last two decades pointed towards the non-existence of definite carboxylates of aluminium. As opposed to this, the only evidence pointing towards possible existence of tri-soaps of aluminium are (i) the observation of Lawrence⁷ showing that three moles of alcohol can be distilled by a reaction between aluminium alkoxides and excess of fatty acids, and (ii) the synthesis of aluminium tri-laurate by Glazer *et al.*⁸ Not only was the existence of tri-derivatives doubted, but the formation of even the mono- and di-soaps of aluminium was not fully established. The position has been summarised in a recent publication by Alexander⁹ in the following words: "On the basis of synthetic and analytical data, obtained from the experiments in non-aqueous media, there is no evidence for the existence of mono- and tri-soaps of aluminium. Aluminium di-soaps of the type $\text{Al}(\text{OR})\text{F}_2$ and $\text{Al}(\text{OH})\text{F}_2$ can be prepared".

Detailed investigations regarding the preparation and properties of aluminium alkoxides¹⁰ has revealed the extraordinary strength of the bridge structure of the following type:

On the basis of the above, the observation that only two moles of the corresponding alcohol can be distilled easily when aluminium ethoxide or isopropoxide is treated with an excess of either a tertiary alcohol itself¹⁰ or its ester¹¹, can be easily explained. Similar observations were made on treating aluminium isopropoxide with three moles of a fatty acid¹². On fractionating the alcohol produced azeotropically with benzene, two moles of the alcohol could be distilled with facility. The replacement of the third alkoxy group, although slow, did, however, occur at a measurable rate and finally all the three moles of alcohol per mole of the alkoxide could be distilled off. The product was found to be stable to heat (up to a temperature of about 200°) under reduced pressure (0.1 mm) and showed an analysis corresponding closely with aluminium tri-soaps. To substantiate the work fully, aluminium isopropoxide was treated with an excess of fatty acids¹³ and after removing the full amount of alcohol (found experimentally to be 3 moles per mole of the alkoxide in each

case) azeotropically, the excess fatty acid was removed either (i) by extracting the excess fatty acid with a suitable solvent like acetone or dioxane from the insoluble tri-soap, or (ii) by distilling the excess fatty acid (in the case of lower fatty acids) under reduced pressure. Tri-derivatives of aluminium with fatty acids (from acetic to stearic acid) have been synthesised and characterised in this manner. The work has been confirmed in a later publication by Gilmour *et al.*¹⁴ by X-ray analysis and also by Schaeffer and coworkers¹⁵ by infrared studies.

Following the above work, it has been further found¹⁶ that mono- and di-alkoxy carboxylates can be prepared by metathetic reaction between aluminium isopropoxide and the calculated amount of the corresponding fatty acid. These alkoxy carboxylates yield the corresponding chloride alkoxides on treatment with acetyl chloride. It has been further shown¹⁷ that the tri-carboxylates of aluminium can also be prepared by the reaction between aluminium isopropoxide and acid anhydrides:

Further work in these laboratories¹⁸ has shown that aluminium chloride carboxylates can be produced by stepwise reactions:

Ebullioscopic measurements of molecular weights of tri-soaps in benzene have shown them to be molecularly dispersed, throwing doubt on the structures suggested recently by Schaeffer *et al.*¹⁵.

In view of the high susceptibility to moisture and hydrolysis of the three above types of carboxylate derivatives, rigorously controlled conditions are required before reproducible data on the physical properties can be obtained. Preliminary work, however, appears to lend support to the gelation theory of Schulman *et al.*¹⁹. Tri-soaps and the mono- and di-alkoxy as well as chloro-soaps of aluminium have been found to provide mobile solutions of low viscosity in hydrocarbon solvents, with a strong tendency of forming stable gels as soon as the derivatives are exposed to hydrolysis. Detailed work on the rate and extent of gelation and on other physical properties like conductivity and dielectric constants is under progress.

In view of the increasing interest in the chemistry of titanium and zirconium, it was thought worthwhile to extend the above work to the carboxylates of these metals also. Compared to the vast literature about aluminium soaps, very little work seems to have been done on the soaps of titanium. Plechner *et al.*²⁰ described the preparation of titanium tetra-soaps by reacting titanium tetrachloride with fatty acids in presence of calcium carbonate.

Repeated attempts to prepare the tetra-soaps by the above reaction always resulted in hydrolysed products, which was not surprising in view of the side formation of water in

the reaction itself²¹. Following the success achieved in the preparation of aluminium tri-soap the corresponding reaction between titanium alkoxides and fatty acids was tried²² for the preparation of tetra-soaps of titanium.

In the above reaction only three moles (approximately) of the alcohol could, however, be distilled even when an excess of the fatty acid was present. Table I records the results obtained in some of the attempts on the above mentioned lines.

TABLE I

Reactions of titanium alkoxides with varying excess of different fatty acids.

Fatty acids.	Alkoxides.	Molar ratio of alkoxide to acid.	Moles of corresponding alcohol replaced per mole of alkoxide.
Acetic	Ti(OPr ⁱ) ₄	1 : 5.0	2.9
Propionic	Ti(OPr ⁱ) ₄	1 : 5.9	2.9
Butyric ⁿ	Ti(OPr ⁱ) ₄	1 : 6.1	3.0
Valeric ⁿ	Ti(OEt) ₄	1 : 4.4	2.7
Lauric	Ti(OEt) ₄	1 : 4.4	2.8
Myristic	Ti(OEt) ₄	1 : 4.37	2.9
Palmitic	Ti(OPr ⁱ) ₄	1 : 4.6	2.8
Palmitic	Ti(OEt) ₄	1 : 4.1	2.8
Stearic	Ti(OPr ⁱ) ₄	1 : 4.0	2.9
Stearic	Ti(OEt) ₄	1 : 3.0	2.9
Stearic	Ti(OBu ⁿ) ₄	1 : 5.1	2.8

The non-replacement of the fourth alkoxy group in these reactions could be explained on the basis of steric hindrance, as already described in the case of aluminium and zirconium alkoxides²³. Titanium alkoxides, like their aluminium and zirconium analogues, have been shown to be polymerized²⁴ and hence based on the structures assigned to these compounds by Caughlan *et al.*²⁵ The associated nature of mono-alkoxy tri-soaps of titanium could possibly involve a bridge structure of the type:

In such a structure, the titanium atoms may be so sterically surrounded that the co-ordination of another fatty acid molecule becomes impossible and hence no further replacement of the alcohol could be achieved.

To test the above explanation, attempts were made to replace the remaining alcohol in the above reaction products with higher alkoxy groups by the well known interchange reactions or with hydroxy groups by treatment with wet benzene. In neither case could an appreciable amount of the alcohol be distilled. In this connection, it may be worth

mentioning that the fourth butoxy group was difficult to be replaced when titanium butoxide was hydrolysed²⁶; an extensive hydrolysis of titanium ethoxide²⁷ was found to result finally in a product of the type, $Ti_2O_3(OEt)_2$.

In order to determine the nature of the end products in the reactions between titanium alkoxides and excess fatty acids, the remaining fatty acid in the product was removed either (i) by extracting with a suitable solvent like acetone, or (ii) by heating the product under reduced pressure. On analysing the products after being submitted to the above treatments, the analysis was found to correspond with titanium derivatives of the type $TiO_x(RCOO)_{4-2x}$ with the value of x nearly 0.5. At the same time analysis of the acetone-soluble portion showed it to be a mixture of the fatty acid and its ester ($RCOOR' + RCOOH$).

The solvent extraction experiments threw fresh light on the above acidolysis reactions, showing that the reaction between titanium alkoxides and fatty acids was not straightforward as in the case of analogous reaction with aluminium alkoxides. At some stage in the above acidolysis experiments, side reactions begin to take place resulting in the formation of organic esters and basic titanium soaps. In order to determine the stage at which complicating side reactions began to take place, titanium alkoxides were first treated with two moles of fatty acids.

It was found that two moles of alcohol could be replaced within a short time. The products on analysis were found to be pure titanium di-soaps of the type, $Ti(OR)_2(OOCR')_2$, indicating the existence of titanium di-soaps as definite chemical entities. Further, the above di-soaps interchanged their alkoxy content with higher alcohols²⁸ by carrying out the reaction in presence of benzene:

When the above di-alkoxy di-soaps of titanium were treated with further amount of fatty acid, complicated side reactions began to take place with the formation of organic ester. The following mechanism (which fits very well with all observed facts) was therefore suggested:

Compared to (iii) the decomposition reaction (ii) appeared to increase as the carbon chain in the fatty acid increases in length. The overall reaction can therefore be represented as:

After having studied in detail the reaction of titanium alkoxides and fatty acids²⁹, the reaction of titanium alkoxides with acetic anhydride was studied³⁰.

Titanium alkoxides were treated both in the presence and absence of an inert medium (benzene) with excess acetic anhydride when the following reaction could be expected to take place:

In no case could a tetra-acetate be obtained and the analysis always corresponded to an oxygen bridge product of the type. $\text{O} \begin{cases} \text{Ti(OAc)}_3 \\ \text{Ti(OAc)}_3 \end{cases}$

To investigate the matter further, the reactions of titanium isopropoxide with acetic anhydride (in the molar ratio of 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3) were tried. In the first two cases, the reaction was highly exothermic, facile and resulted in the formation of pure mono- and di-acetate derivatives:

The reaction of titanium isopropoxide with three moles of acetic anhydride, however, always resulted finally in the formation of a product which corresponded in analysis to

indicating that after the formation of the di-acetate derivative, the reaction became complicated. The above product on treatment with further acetic anhydride yielded the basic tri-acetate.

The above facts can be explained on the following simple mechanism:

Further, the above study has been extended to the reaction of titanium tetrachloride and fatty acids³¹. These reactions were found to be even more complicated than the corresponding reactions of fatty acids with titanium tetra-alkoxides. Very long period (up to 100 hours) of refluxing in benzene were required before the hydrogen chloride could be driven out of the reaction mixture. Also, the titanium chloride appeared to catalyse some side-condensation reactions (cf. catalytic power of aluminium chloride for a large variety of organic reactions). Therefore, to elucidate the nature of the above complicated reaction, the lowest member of the fatty acid series, acetic acid was chosen. In this case also, the reaction has been observed to be simple and straightforward up to the formation of titanium dichloride di-acetate. With the interaction of the third mole of acetic acid and the formation of titanium monochloride tri-acetate, decomposition, however, begins to take

place, finally resulting in the formation of a mixture of basic di- and mono- acetate of the type:

It has been therefore referred that the reaction of fatty acids with titanium tetrachloride is similar to that with titanium alkoxides.

Finally, the reaction of titanium tetrachloride with acetic anhydride was attempted with a view to preparing the tetra-acetate. Results similar to the above, however, were obtained and the final product was always found to correspond in analysis to a basic tri-acetate:

Thus the treatment of the tetra-derivatives of titanium, TiCl_4 or Ti(OR)_4 , with acetic acid-anhydride mixture always results in a basic tri-acetate. Further, it was found that treatment of hydrolysed titanium alkoxides or tetrachloride (or even hydrated titanium dioxide) with acetic anhydride yields the same basic tri-acetate product.³²

TABLE II

No. Reactions.	Analysis of the product.			
	Found.		Calc. for	
	%Ti.	%OAc.	$\text{O} \begin{cases} \text{Ti(OAc)}_3 \\ \text{Ti(OAc)}_3 \end{cases}$	
		%Ti.	%OAc.	
1. $\text{Ti(OPri)}_4 + \text{Ac}_2\text{O}$	20.55	76.3		
2. $\text{Ti(OEt)}_4 + \text{Ac}_2\text{O}$	20.62	76.5		
3. $\text{TiCl}_4 + \text{Ac}_2\text{O} + \text{AcOH}$	20.56	78.2	20.55	76.0
4. Hydrolysed $\text{Ti(OPri)}_4 + \text{Ac}_2\text{O}$	20.40	76.5		
5. $\text{Ti(OH)}_4 + \text{Ac}_2\text{O}$	21.20	75.8		

Thus it appears that the basic tri-acetate is always the end product, whether we treat titanium tetra-derivative (like tetra-alkoxide or tetrachloride) or more hydrolysed titanium derivatives, with acetic anhydride or a mixture of acetic acid and acetic anhydride.

Zirconium isopropoxide and excess of a fatty acid (stearic, palmitic, lauric and caproic) yield basic tricarboxylates³³, $(\text{R.CO}_2)_3\text{Zr.O.Zr}(\text{CO}_2\text{R})_3$, which remain unchanged on repeated crystallisation from dioxan. The reaction was carried out in refluxing benzene under a column so that the isopropyl alcohol produced could be removed azeotropically with benzene. The alcohol in the azeotrope was estimated. Even when the ratio zirconium isopro-

oxide: fatty acid was more than 1:4, not more than 4.5 moles of alcohol per mole of the crystalline isopropoxide $Zr(OPri)_4$, $PriOH$ distilled azeotropically. It thus appeared that the replacement of the fifth alcoholic group might be slow owing to steric hindrance, or that a side reaction occurred owing to which a portion of the replaceable alcohol in the alkoxide could not be distilled. For example, the fact that 4.5 moles of alcohol are replaced can be explained simply if the main reaction is represented as:

The reaction of zirconium tetra-isopropoxide with palmitic and stearic acids was carried out stepwise:

These replacements were rapid and the benzene-isopropyl alcohol azeotrope distilled quickly. Tri-isopropoxyzirconium monostearate and monopalmitate and diisopropoxyzirconium distearate and dipalmitate were isolated in pure states. These are stable to heat under reduced pressure, but are susceptible to atmospheric moisture.

The di-soaps were treated with fatty acids (palmitic or stearic) in the molar ratio 1:1. On fractionation almost 1 mole of alcohol distilled azeotropically, indicating the simple reaction:

From the remaining solution, benzene was distilled off under reduced pressure and the solid products were analysed. The zirconium content corresponded to the monoisopropoxy tricarboxylate, but the isopropoxy content was considerably below theoretical. Further, the isopropoxy content depended on the amount of heating to which the products were subjected. If the monoisopropoxy tristearate decomposes:

the analytical results could be explained. The product from reaction (vi) was treated with dry dioxan; the crystallised zirconium soap on analysis corresponded to a mixture of $ZrO(R.CO_2)_2$ and $Zr(OPri)(R.CO_2)_3$. The sweet-smelling dioxan-soluble portion was a mixture of the fatty acid and ester; on analysis a sample conformed with the decomposition (vii).

The isolation of the isopropoxyzirconium tristearate is therefore only possible by carrying out the reaction at a low temperature:

The correctness of the overall reaction mechanism (iii) has been further demonstrat-

ed³⁴ by refluxing an equimolecular mixture of the isopropoxyzirconium tristearate and the tetrastearate, whereupon the reaction (ix) takes place:

Having failed to prepare zirconium tetra-soaps by the above reaction, we tried to make zirconium tetrachloride react with fatty acids (stearic, palmitic, and myristic). Although the tetrachloride is not appreciably soluble in benzene, it slowly reacted with fatty acids when refluxed and hydrogen chloride evolved freely. Refluxing was continued until evolution of hydrogen chloride became negligible, when the solution gave colorless crystals of tetra-soaps:

Repeated crystallisation from benzene did not noticeably change the analysis of the product whose identity is thus confirmed.

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